

Hermitan matrices based malicious cognitive radio detection and bayesian method for detecting primary user emulation attack

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ABSTRACT

Cognitive radio (CR) is a facilitating technology to efficiently deal with the spectrum scarceness, and it will significantly enhance the spectrum deployment of upcoming wireless transmission method. Security is a significant concern, although not well tackle in cognitive radio networks (CRN). In CR networks, this approach regard as a security issue happen from primary user emulation attack (PUEA). A PUEA attacker forwards an emulated primary signal and defraud the CR users to avoid them from accessing spectrum holes. Here, we introduce a Hermitan matrices based malicious cognitive radio (CMCR) detection and Bayesian method for detecting PUEA attack in the CRN. In this approach, the Bayesian method is used for detecting the PUEA attack. The trust analyzer evaluates the CR trust. Here, the node trust value is computed by node activeness and inactiveness, degree of data transmission, and hermitan matrices verification. In addition, the Hermitan Matrices method is used to detect the malicious CR user in the CRN. The simulation outcomes propose that the CMCR leads to improve the performance in terms of better detection ratio, minimized the possibility of miss detection ratio. Furthermore, it minimized the possibility of false alarm in the CRN.

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1. INTRODUCTION

The rapid propagation of smart devices and the management of the spectral band in the radio communication method have result in an insufficiency of frequencies. To overcome this problem, the design of dynamic spectrum entrée during cognitive radio has become quite attractive. In cognitive radio networks (CRN), two class of spectrum users for example primary users (PUs) and the cognitive radio (CR) user [1]. In CRN, a malicious communicates signals with features which imitate PU to avoid CR users from transmitting. This type of attack is known as a primary user emulation attack (PUEA) attack. Malicious users can develop vulnerabilities in CRNs and origin heavy function degradation through denial of service attacks [2]. Throughout function, CRs expend a significant amount of time to recognize idle channels for communication. Additionally, CRs also necessitate additional security methods to avoid malicious attacks [3].

The CR technology offers the capability for wireless devices to develop the PU, CR user should empty the channel while a PU is identified. Therefore, spectrum sensing is one of the most technological challenges

in CRN to discover the spectrum holes [4]. Cooperative spectrum sensing (CSS) has been introduced to defeat the destructive effect of shadowing, multipath fading, and hidden terminal issues. In CSS, several CR users forward local sensing information for example, evaluated energy or one bit conclusion to the neighbors otherwise to the fusion center (FC). Established on the nature of the obtained information, FC selects hard combination otherwise soft combination system to decide the status of channel [5]. The cryptographic approaches may raise the transmission, storage and computation cost through frankly raising the communication delay [6].

Presently, the authenticity of the devices otherwise applications can be calculated by the trust value. The network trust is discrete as a computing parameter which computes the validity of a detailed node by its earlier or accessible communications lacking raising the cryptographic procedures. Thus, an efficient method to make sure a secure message method is a trust based procedure [7]. It improves the security lacking further raising the network delay as well as overhead. Unfortunately, trusted security methods have not been systematically recognized and are still in their untimely stages in a CRN [8]. A secure and trusted routing is used to distinguish the malicious nodes in the CRN. A trust analyser (TA) is proposed between the CR nodes. The TA handles the table of entire transmitting nodes while computing the trust value through the social impact theory optimizer [9].

This article is structured as follows: section 2 describes the related research work regarding CRN with PUEA detection. Section 3 explains the Hermitan Matrices based malicious cognitive radio detection and Bayesian method for detecting PUEA attack in the CRN. Section 4 contains simulation results of SPUEA and CMCR schemes. Finally, section 5 exist the conclusion.

A game theoretical framework is used to detect the PUEA. A game of imperfect information among the secondary users (Sus), it does not interchange game information among them against the opponents creating the PUEA. The SUs plays as a grand association which attains synchronization every SUs create the same decisions lacking collaboration [10]. Signal activity pattern (SAP) system does not essential any a priori knowledge of PU. It obtains the activity pattern of a signal via spectrum sensing. It rebuilds the monitored signal activity pattern via a reconstruction model. primary user emulation (PUE) detection system that obtains the SAP of PU signal transmitters. However, this approach can't detect the PUEA [11]. The channel-tap power is applied as a radio-frequency fingerprint to entirely recognise PUEAs. The cross-layer intelligent learning ability of a SU is demoralized to launch detection databases through seamlessly joining the quick detection [12]. Belief propagation defence strategy that avoids the distribution of additional network. In this strategy, every SU computes the local function and the compatibility operation calculates the messages, interactions messages and calculates the beliefs until conjunction. The PUE attacker is identified by the belief threshold. If the beliefs is below a threshold, the uncertain can be identified as a PUE attacker [13]. Malicious users can cause heavy performance degradation by denial of service (DoS) attacks. Proactive model predictive control based medium access control protocols for CRs can accelerate the idle channel identity through forecasting channels future states [14].

A smart primary user emulation attacker (SPUEA) that does not create the channel busy all the times through taking into account the attacker as well as PU activity parameters also traffics. In preparation, an attacker may not misbehave every time, since if the attackers inhabit spectrum or else report false results, the attackers will be jammed simply through applying the SPUEA method. The function for the detection of spectrum sensing of false alarm probabilities and gets the SU throughput [15]. A cooperative multiband spectrum sensing approach is operating in the presence of malicious users. Cooperative spectrum sensing is enhancing the recognition operation and enhance the aggregate the attainable throughput [16]. A nonparametric Bayesian method for identifying the PUE attacks. The infinite Gaussian mixture model is accepted and an adjusted collapsed Gibbs sampling method is introduced to categorise the extracted fingerprints [17].

Database assisted frequency domain action recognition approach for detecting PUEA by application of action recognition techniques. Wireless communication functioning across a CRN and it utilize a relational database. This approach detect the PUEA by an energy detection in a particular frequency band. This strategy applies a relational database to record the motion-related feature vectors of PU on this frequency band. While an interrupted communication does not have a competition record in the database, this communication is considered from the PUEA [18]. Cooperative spectrum sensing approach is used to detect the existence of PUEA. In this approach, the joining weights are optimized with the aim of enhancing the available channel detection probability. It examine the influence of the channel estimation errors on the detection probability [19]. An emotion recognition system applying a deep learning method to receive a mel-spectrogram. In this approach, the support vector machine is used to classified the emotions [20]. Harmony search optimization algorithm is used for optimal route selection in the network [21].

Single input fuzzy logic controller (SIFLC) with gradient descent algorithm (GDA) and particle swarm optimization (PSO) for improving the routing efficiency [22]. Multi-feature-based deep convolutional neural networks which recognizes the facial expression. The input are preprocessed and improved through three filtering methods such as Gaussian, Wiener, and adaptive mean filtering. It further functional local binary

pattern that extracts the facial points of every facial expression. The deep features assists to remove the local data lacking acquiring a higher computational effort [23].

A tracking method which merge regression tree and Kalman smoother filtering. Regression tree is recommended by received signal strength indicator. This method to resolve the mapping relation between capacity and the target location. The predicted location measured as the identified information by the Kalman smoother algorithm [24]. Energy-efficiency in a shared based target tracking method can be reached by two methods such as sensing-related and communication-related. In this approach, a prediction algorithm to optimize communication and sensing functions. This method can minimized the energy utilization in the wireless sensor network (WSN) [25]. A swarm intellect optimization technique is used to detect the mischievous nodes and enhance the authentication. Here, the cluster heads (CHs) are chosen by the node weight. Observing behavior, observing energy utilization and fake route ads parameters are determined by the Mischievous nodes [26]. The predictive parser method is applied to verify the sensor authentication. Furthermore, an Elliptical curve cryptography algorithm to reject the eaves dropping attack [27].

2. HERMITAN MATRICES BASED MALICIOUS COGNITIVE RADIO DETECTION AND BAYESIAN METHOD FOR DETECTING PUEA ATTACK IN THE CRN

This approach contains number of CR user, malicious CR, PU and PUEA with a FC. The CR can identify the channel regularly and execute local determinations on the existence of the PU along with its hold clarification. Figure 1 shows the architecture of proposed system. This Figure 1 contains, FC, PU, PUEA, CR and malicious CR.

Figure 1. Architecture of proposed system

In this approach, the local spectrum is observed through the received signal strength indicator (RSSI) method. Recognized on the receiver R obtained signal, the distance distinctive R from a transmitter T is work out related the RSSI method. The CR users are inspired as receivers, and any PU; or else, PUEAs are considered as feasible transmitters. Usually, to avoid any forthcoming collision between PU and CRs signals, the PU dictates the entire CR nodes to make the channel clearly; as a result, it will be able to transferring hold data.

The PUEA try to win for the PU signal characteristics to attain at the channel resources. Here, we compute the RSSI is shown in (1).

$$RSSI = -10 \log_{10}(dist) + AP \tag{1}$$

Here k indicates the path-loss exponent of broadcasting, $dist$ indicates the distance between T and R , in addition, AP is the acquired power. A PUEA is present in the CRN that effort to evade the CR users from obtaining the spectrum holes. The local result of the entire sensing nodes will be broadcast a one-bit result to FC. Initially, the PU forward the signal to CR. Then, the CR received the signal and forward PU signals to FC. The FC before gets the PU signal, it checks the CR is real or not by the hermitan matrices with trust value. Figure 2 explains a Hermitan matrices based CR Verification. Thus, a Hermitan matrix is definite as:

$$A = A^T \tag{2}$$

that is the diagonal elements of a Hermitian matrix is real numbers, while other components maybe complex. If A is Hermitian, then as $A = A^T$:

$$A = \begin{bmatrix} d & k + ai \\ k - ai & e \end{bmatrix} \tag{3}$$

Figure 2. Hermitian matrices based CR verification

here,
 d =CR identity.
 k =secret key.
 e =PU identity.
 i =imaginary unit.

The secret key (k) computation is specified in (4):

$$\begin{aligned} K &= \log_2 d^R \\ K &= R \frac{\log d}{\log 2} \end{aligned} \tag{4}$$

here, d indicates the CR identity and R indicates the random number.

Here, a CR desires to admittance an unoccupied band, node computes the value of trust (VT) to demanding CRs through authenticating it with the pre-set thresholds. If the CR of VT is higher than the threshold, next the CR is trusted and allowable to admittance the band. A trust analyzer is continued which preserves the evidence of all nodes factors in its routing. Here, the node trust value is computed by node activeness and inactiveness, degree of data transmission, and hermitian matrices verification. Every node trust value exist between 0 and 1. Here, the trust value 0.3 represents that node is a malicious and 0.3 to 0.4 value nodes are chances to exist that node is a compromised nodes in the network. Breadth first search (BFS) tree method is used for dynamically determine the trust threshold between sender and receiver. If confirms the CR is a real then FC obtained the PU signals from CR and verified the PU signal by the Bayesian model. Figure 3 explains a PUEA attack detection in the WSN.

Figure 3. PUEA attack detection

In CSS, compute the RSSI of each CR user is communicated to the FC to assemble a decision concerning the present or non-present the PU signal. The out turn signal (OS) at the FC is specified in (5). Here, β denotes the preset threshold.

$$OS = RSSI \geq \beta \quad (5)$$

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Here, 100 CR users apply RSSI detection through $M=25$ samples in a detection interval. Moreover, the possibility of a false alarm for the threshold value is 0.1. The network simulator is used for detects the PUEA attacker and malicious CR user in the CRN. Figure 4 describes the error possibility between PU and CR for the CMCR and SPUEA schemes based on signal to noise ratio (SNR). The SPUEA approach SNR value is increased the possibility of the error also increased. Here, the CMCR has the feasibility of lesser error possibility since the hermitian matrices is used to detect the PUEA.

Figure 5 illustrates the false alarm possibility of the centralized multicast contention resolution (CMCR) scheme and SPUEA scheme. Here, the CMCR scheme improves the network function since it results in the smallest amount of false alarms. However, SPUEA scheme increases the false alarm when it increases the SNR.

Figure 6 explains the error possibility of the SPUEA scheme and CMCR scheme based on node density respectively. Here, the CMCR has the feasibility of lesser error possibility since the hermitian matrices is used to detect the PUEA. Figure 7 explains the miss detection possibility of CMCR scheme and SPUEA scheme based on node density respectively. Here, the proposed CMCR has feasibility of lesser miss detection since the CMCR technique hermitian matrices is used to detect the PUEA efficiently. Furthermore, malicious CR is detected by the Trust analysis method. However, SPUEA scheme raises the miss detection when it increases the node density since it can't distinguish the PUEA completely.

Figure 4. Error possibility of SPUEA and CMCR schemes based on SNR

Figure 5. False alarm possibility of SPUEA and CMCR schemes based on SNR

Figure 6. Error possibility of SPUEA and CMCR schemes based on node density

Figure 7. Miss detection possibility of SPUEA and CMCRC schemes based on node density

4. CONCLUSION

This paper launched the concept for detecting the malicious CR and PUEA in the CRN. A trust analyzer is efficiently resolved malicious CR user through exploiting the behavioural features of every CR user. This paper presents a Hermitian Matrices based malicious Cognitive radio detection and Bayesian method for detecting PUEA attack in the CRN. In this approach, the Bayesian method is used for detecting the PUEA attack. The trust analyzer evaluates the CR trust. The node trust value is computed by node activeness and inactiveness, degree of data transmission, and hermitian matrices verification. In addition, the Hermitian Matrices method is used to detect the malicious CR user in the CRN. The simulation outcomes explained that the CMCRC leads to improve the performance in terms of better detection ratio, minimized the possibility of miss detection ratio. Furthermore, it minimized the possibility of false alarm in the CRN.

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